

Management of Liver Biloma after Gunshot Thoraco-Abdominal Injury. A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

During the Russian armed aggression against Ukraine, a large number of Ukrainian civilians were injured or killed since 2022. The rate of penetrating abdominal injuries during active military action varies from 2% to 15%, the small intestine, colon, liver and intra-abdominal vessels are most often affected. Patients with gunshot abdominal injuries and liver lacerations are more likely to have specific complications such as necrosis or abscesses, bilomas or biliary leakage. Ultrasound-guided drainage is a common treatment of biloma, but persistent bile leakage requires further endoscopic or surgical treatment and remains an important issue that needs to be resolved.

We present the case of a 22-year-old man who got a penetrating gunshot thoraco-abdominal wound with damage to the VI-VII segments of the liver as a result of military operations. Among other surgical interventions, the patient underwent cholecystectomy with external drainage of the common bile duct. The case was complicated by the formation of liver and subhepatic bilomas, which required drainage under ultrasound control. Prolonged bile secretion from the drainage in the amount of about 100-150 ml per day prompted the search for a solution to this problem and providing of endoscopic internal bile drainage. It allowed to terminate bile leakage and remove drainage from the liver and subhepatic space.

The case is noteworthy, as the literature review found few reports of bilomas in patients after gunshot injuries of the liver and no cases were found that were the result of military operations.

Endobiliary drainage in a patient with a gunshot liver injury allows to effectively treat biliary leakage. The use of such endoscopic method in the treatment of patients with gunshot liver injuries complicated by bilomas is an actual issue that needs to be studied.

Keywords: Liver injury; Biloma; Biliary leakage; Endobiliary drainage; Stenting, ERCP

INTRODUCTION

The rate of penetrating abdominal injuries during active military action varies from 2% to 15%, the small intestine, colon, liver and intra-abdominal vessels are most often affected. The most common organs injured are the small bowel (50%), large bowel (40%), liver (30%), and intra-abdominal vessels (25%) ^[10]. Gunshot penetrating injuries of the abdominal cavity associated with liver damage have a number of features compared to liver damage in blunt abdominal trauma. Thus, one study analyzed 879 patients with liver injuries. A significantly larger part of patients with gunshot wounds underwent surgery (82.7 vs. 36.1% patients with blunt abdominal trauma). Gunshot trauma was associated with significantly more liver-related complications (40.7% vs. 27.4%), specifically liver necrosis/abscess (18.5% vs. 7.1%) and bile leak or biloma (12.3% vs. 5.3%) ^[9]. It should be noted that this study was conducted in peacetime on the territory where there were no active hostilities.

Another study conducted in an active combat zone (the Syrian war, between 2012 and 2013) analyzed 325 cases of gunshot abdominal injuries. The great majority of patients (82.1%) are young men aged 19 to 35 years. The most patients had explosive mechanism of trauma (56.3%), and a smaller number (43.3%) had gunshot wounds. At the same time, multiple intra-abdominal injuries were more frequently observed in patients with gunshot wounds (51.1% vs. 45.3% in patients with explosive trauma of the abdominal cavity). 81.5% of all patients with penetrating gunshot abdominal injury underwent surgery ^[1].

Bilomas and biliary leakage are common complications of liver injuries. Most of them can be successfully treated by percutaneous drainage under radiological control ^[4]. However, in the case of persistent biliary leakage, patients require endoscopic or surgical interventions.

Thus, gunshot abdominal injuries with liver damage are an important problem in times of active hostilities, especially in young men, who are the majority of the wounded. Complications such as bilomas and biliary leakage sometimes require not only percutaneous drainage, but also further endoscopic or surgical intervention.

CASE PRESENTATION

A 22-year-old male patient obtained a penetrating gunshot thoraco-abdominal wound with damage to the VI-VII liver segments as a result of hostilities. Liver damage class IV. 20 hours after the injury, he was transported to the nearest surgical hospital, where he underwent a CT scan (Figure 1) and surgical intervention: laparoscopy, conversion, suturing of liver segments VI-VII, cholecystectomy, biliary drainage, drainage of abdominal cavity, and Bühlau drainage of the right pleural cavity.

The patient received antibiotic therapy (Ceftriaxone 1.0 IV b.i.d.), analgesics and infusion therapy, pain management.

Figure 1. CT scan on the first day after injury. Note the soft tissue defects of the lateral chest and abdominal wall, as well as the heterogeneous structure of the VI-VII liver segments with air inclusions.

He was transported to Vinnytsia Regional Clinical Hospital five days after the injury. During the examination, the patient complained of dyspnoea, pain in the right side of the chest, which increased with breathing. Glasgow Coma Scale 14/15, pulse 72/min, rhythmic, blood pressure 140/80 mmHg, the axillary temperature 37.8 °C. Chest examination showed severe tenderness in the area of the entry wound, weakness of breathing in the lower right lung. Bühlau drainage on the right side shows mild serous hemorrhagic discharge, and the tightness is maintained. Abdominal examination showed slight tenderness in the area of the laparotomy wound and in the right subcostal region. Symptoms of peritoneal irritation are negative. Up to 20 ml of bile per day was discharged by biliary drainage, no discharge from the abdominal cavity. No other clinically significant abnormalities were found.

Laboratory tests: hemoglobin 100 g/l (N 120-150 g/l), red blood cells $3.3 \times 10^{12}/l$ (N $4-5 \times 10^{12}/l$), leukocytes $8.5 \times 10^9/l$ (N $4-9 \times 10^9/l$), glucose 4.4 mmol/l (N 3.3-5.5 mmol/l), bilirubin 11.1 $\mu\text{mol}/l$ (N 5-20, 5 $\mu\text{mol}/l$), potassium 3.9 mmol/l (N 3.5-5.1 mmol/l), sodium 132 mmol/l (N 130-156 mmol/l), urea 5.6 mmol/l (N 3.3-8.6 mmol/l), creatinine 67 $\mu\text{mol}/l$ (35-124 $\mu\text{mol}/l$).

The chest X-ray revealed incomplete expansion of the right lung, its compression; decreased transparency of the basal parts due to interlobular pleural effusion as a result of hemothorax; elevation of the right diaphragm dome, and obscuration of the sinuses.

CT scans of the chest and abdomen without contrast demonstrated signs of contusion of the right lung and liver, fragmentary fractures of the 8th and 9th right ribs, right-sided cystic pleural effusion, drainage in the pleural cavity and abdominal cavity, fluid collections in the soft tissues of the right hypochondrium. A heterogeneous area with air inclusions with size of 10.4 x 10 x 9.8 cm without clear margins was detected in the right lobe of the liver (Figure 2).

Figure 2. CT on the sixth day after the injury.

Surgical debridement with drainage of the hemobiloma of the right lateral abdominal wall was performed.

On the 11th day after the injury, a control ultrasound of the abdomen showed a fluid collection in the subhepatic area with a size of 48x30 mm, a heterogeneous, mostly fluid formation of the VII liver segment subcapsularly with a size of 90x48x51 mm. There was also a minimal amount of fluid in the right pleural cavity.

On the same day, percutaneous US-guided draining of the liver biloma and biloma of subhepatic space was performed.

On the control CT scan on the 18th day after the injury, the heterogeneous area of the liver parenchyma decreased in size. The fluid component in the subhepatic space was not detected (**Figure 3**).

Figure 3. CT on the 18th day after injury.

About 50 ml of bile is discharged from the liver drainage per day, and up to 100 ml of bile per day from the subhepatic drainage. There was no discharge from the common bile duct by drainage tube. On the 21st day after the injury, the drainage from the common bile duct was blocked, on the 28th day it was removed. At the same time, active bile secretion through the bilomas drainages in a stable volume remains.

Due to persistent bile leakage endoscopic surgical procedure (ERCP, endobiliary stenting) was performed on day 48. A 10 Fr 10 cm PTE stent was installed (**Figures 4, 5**). In the postoperative period, acute post-ERCP pancreatitis occurred, which required the placement of a peridural catheter and treatment in the ICU for 3 days.

Within two weeks after endobiliary stenting, bile leakage through the liver biloma drainage progressively decreased and stopped. Drains from the liver biloma were removed on the 70th day after the injury, and from the subhepatic space - on the 75th day.

On the 130th day after the injury (1.5 months after the removal of the bilomas drains), the stent was removed from the biliary tract. The patient's health has been fully restored.

Figure 4. Cholangiogram with marked area of contrast extravasation.

Figure 5. Condition after stenting:
A - PTE stent in the common bile duct; B - area of subhepatic biloma; C - external drainage of biloma

DISCUSSION

A clinical case of treatment of a patient with biloma of the liver and subhepatic space after a gunshot wound is presented. Percutaneous drainage of the biloma resulted in prolonged biliary leakage, which prompted the search for closure of biliary fistulas.

Bilomas and biliary leakage are common complications of liver injury. Their frequency relates to the severity of the liver injury^[12]. Both intrahepatic and extrahepatic bile ducts may be injured after gunshot trauma to the liver. The volume of bile leakage and its duration depend on the caliber of the damaged bile duct^[13]. Clinical manifestations of

liver injury complications, especially bilomas, may appear a few days after the trauma. Imaging methods, such as ultrasound, CT scan, MRI, and MRCP, have a decisive role in the diagnosis of these complications. For example, ultrasound, as the cheapest imaging method, allows detecting fluid collections and evaluating their substance (e.g., detritus or blood clots in the biloma) ^[6]. In addition to clearly demarcated fluid collections, CT scans can show whether the accumulation has capsules or not, and can also differentiate between postoperative seroma, hematoma, abscess, lymphocele, liver cyst, or pseudocyst. MRCP makes it possible to detect the source of biloma ^[14]. According to the literature review, the optimal time for repeated radiological examinations is 7-10 days after liver damage ^[7]. However, on our opinion, these time frames may be shifted depending on clinical manifestations.

Most post-traumatic liver bilomas may be successfully treated by percutaneous drainage under radiological control ^[4]. According to the literature, external biliary fistulas after biloma drainage spontaneously close three weeks after the placement of external drainage, but it depends on the character of the injury ^[11].

However, in the case of prolonged and persistent biliary flow, like in this case, patients require endoscopic or surgical interventions. Indications for further invasive treatment of biliary leakage are bile excretion of more than 50 ml/d, which lasts for more than two weeks, or a large bile discharge (300-400 ml/d), regardless of the duration ^[5].

Endoscopic methods, such as ERCP, sphincterotomy alone, internal biliary drainage with or without sphincterotomy, and nasobiliary drainage with or without sphincterotomy, have proven to be effective methods of treating liver bilomas and biliary leakage. Thus, some authors report 89% success rate of therapeutic ERCP in the treatment of post-traumatic liver bilomas ^[2].

On our opinion, patients with post-traumatic liver bilomas due to penetrating gunshot wounds should undergo endoscopic endobiliary drainage after percutaneous drainage operations as soon as possible (as far the access to specialized facilities or equipment allows). This opinion is supported by the few reports in the literature on the high efficacy of early ERCP (within 24 hours) in the treatment of post-traumatic bilomas and biliary leakage ^[3]. Pain management is also very important ^[15,16,17].

CONCLUSIONS

Patients with gunshot liver injuries usually have more severe liver damage, which is accompanied by a higher risk of complications such as biloma and biliary leakage. Imaging techniques such as ultrasound and CT scan play a decisive role in the diagnosis of these complications. Percutaneous drainage is an effective method of treating liver bilomas, but prolonged or massive biliary leakage requires the addition of invasive therapeutic methods. Therapeutic ERCP is a highly effective method of treating biliary leakage. The issue of early ERCP in the treatment of gunshot liver injuries and their complications remains relevant.

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